

WRITING SKILLS AND ARTISTIC TOOLS

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Abstract. *Shukur Kholmirzaev, as the owner of a unique personal artistic style, avoids criticism, one-sidedness, narrative. Although he is stingy with words, he only achieves full and bright delivery to the reader. However, sometimes his works give the impression that they are not finished. The reader waits for the continuation of the work. He does not draw portraits of heroes. It seems that the main focus is on character creation, which forces the reader to think and think deeply. The judgment passed on the heroes of the work is brought to the reader's attention. This article discusses the unique artistic skills of the writer Shukur Kholmirzaev and his ability to effectively use artistic tools.*

Keywords: *artistry, writing skills, portrait, image tools, the idea of the work, the spiritual world of the hero, the role of word art, artistic intention, creative process, individual style, the language of the work, work, national an mothers.*

Shukur Kholmirzaev is one of the great writers born in 100 years. Writer was not afraid to speak the truth in any difficult situation. Even in difficult times, his faith in literature and life was strong.

It is known that Shukur Kholmirzaev's work is characterized by its richness and means of expression [3, 21]. This situation undoubtedly confirms that the writer used the possibilities of artistic language extensively and comprehensively. It should be noted that the language of the writer's stories has a colorful character. This shows the ability of the writer to use the possibilities of the Uzbek language in what way and in what way.

It is known that the artistry of a writer and an artist are compared to each other. Because both are artists. And the goals are the same, to depict life, but different only in terms of the tool of depicting life. An artist uses a brush and paint, and a writer uses words to achieve their goals. We linger in front of a wonderful piece of art created by a master artist. A view of life drawn in it with colorful paints occupies our thoughts, affects our emotions, and gives pleasure to our hearts. At the moment, such a situation can be experienced even after getting acquainted with the works that came out from under the pen of a talented writer.

The writer is also an artist. It is necessary to draw life, human character, the environment in which they act, facts through short, concise and clear sentences through the means of words.

There are many opinions and opinions of artists, as well as wishes and suggestions based on the experience of artistic creation, regarding the clear and precise drawing of the depicted reality. In his comments to young writers, it is repeatedly emphasized that the artist should first of all know deeply about the reality he is writing about and that his expression should be clear and reasonable. At this point, we considered it necessary to cite only the most appropriate of them, without quoting all of them, adopting the thoughts of the writer. In particular, we think that these words of the Russian writer A.M. Gorky are consistent with the above ideas and express the rational essence of all of them.

"It is extremely difficult to find precise words and arrange them in such a way that they mean a lot with few words, because words must be compact and thoughts must be detailed and

wide, that is, vivid pictures from words. the character of the person being described, the flow and tone of the words should be immediately imprinted on the reader's memory. It's one thing to "slap" people and objects with words, it's another thing to depict them "plastically" alive..." [2, 120]

In order to vividly describe people and things, every word, every sentence should be concise in its place and serve the meaning that the writer wants to convey. Only then does the reader feel as if he sees the events and incidents described by the writer with his own eyes, and even feels like he is participating in this event. After all, the work written by such a writer affects the reader's worldview and helps to understand the complexity of life.

Shukur Kholmirzaev is a popular writer. He is a creator who knows the language of the people well and is in harmony with the language of the people. That is why the language of the writer's works is used in folk tone. This undoubtedly ensured that the language of the writer's works was simple, fluent, and understandable. In particular, "Oghir tosh kochsa" (If a heavy stone moves), "Last station", "Make a bridge", "Almonds bloomed in winter", "Birds returned from the village", "Navroz" related to the writer's artistic language linguopoetics. We witnessed this directly in the process of learning the language of stories such as Navroz. Shukur Kholmirzaev undoubtedly pays attention to the possibilities of the vernacular in ensuring that the language of each of his works is thorough, mature, and perfect. His ability to use folk wisdom, proverbs, proverbs and various folk oral materials is commendable.

Shukur Kholmirzaev is a writer with a very refined taste. He chooses every word with a delicate taste and observation. That is why the language of works is melodious and attractive. So, the writer's creativity is colorful and colorful, and accordingly, the language of the writer's works is distinguished by the fact that it is expressed in a unique tone.

Learning the language of a work of art requires the artist to be able to choose his own tools of artistic language, to be able to use them appropriately and productively. Undoubtedly, the researcher should pay attention to this side of the issue in order to study the writer's artistic skill and unique style.

In the process of studying the work of Shukur Kholmirzaev, we will have the opportunity to determine the possibilities of using the lexical and methodological tools available in the Uzbek language. It should be noted that the writer skillfully used all lexical and methodological tools available in the national language. It is especially characteristic of his use of figurative language tools, resourcefulness and cleverness in using words specific to oral speech, use of new words and phrases, as well as the skill of using idioms.

Thus, Shukur Kholmirzaev is a respected writer. The reader who reads each of his works will be delighted and drown in the ocean of happiness. Undoubtedly, this situation is the language of his works that made the writer famous. It is the writer's own style. In short, learning the language of Shukur Kholmirzaev's works is the demand of the times. Through this, we will have the opportunity to study the writer's contribution to the development of the Uzbek literary language and the language of fiction.

It is known that Shukur Kholmirzaev effectively used the visual means of the Uzbek language in order to enrich the language of his works. One of such artistic descriptive tools is periphrasis, by using which the writer made the language of his works colorful and melodious.

One of the characteristic features of artistic prose is that each artist uses words to describe the specific qualities and signs of a certain concept, and to reveal its characteristic features. These pictorial expressions are typical for the writer's work, they are applied to each of Sh. Kholmirzaev's

works in a unique way and attract the reader's attention. For example: “Keyin amar nomiga bitta maktub bitilgan edi. Janob oliylari maktubni o‘qib, yoshlarni o‘z huzurlariga chaqirdilar”.- "Then one letter was written to Amar. His Highness read the letter and called the young people to his presence". [6, 8]

In the cited text, the writer used the combination of *his highnesses* to avoid using the word *amir* again. This, in turn, is a unique way of avoiding repetition of words. Because repetition of a single word itself damages the clarity and fluency of the speech. It seems that accuracy, fluency is the decoration of speech, and it is directly related to a person's good understanding of the meaning of words and clear imagination.

Starting from his first stories, the writer introduced the image of heroes who have their place in life, a certain social position, and a unique character.

Shukur Kholmirzaev is a creator of today's Uzbek literature with a unique style. The characters in his works are distinguished by the diversity of their spiritual world. Uzbek aspects in the characters of the heroes are worthy of praise for being raised to the level of universality, because those aspects that gave a special meaning and charm to the spiritual world of the heroes, with the events of our day and age, that is, the lifestyle of our contemporaries, joys and anxieties, moreover, are directly related to the new criteria of life that are being formed, as Shkur Kholmirzaev skillfully infuses these qualities into the spiritual world of his characters, it is certainly the skill of this writer, moreover, it is a specific feature of Uzbek literature of the 20th century. is also an achievement.

In general, Shukur Kholmirzaev effectively uses artistic tools not only in his stories and short stories, but also in his novels and dramatic works.

REFERENCES

1. Boboyev T. Sources of literary studies.- Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2001.-560 p.
2. Gorky M. About literature. Literary and critical articles.- Tashkent: Ozadabiynashrp, 1962.- p. 120.
3. Normurodov R. Shukur Kholmirzaev's artistic language skills. Philol. sciences. name dissertation. - T, 2003, 32b
4. Sultanova M. About the style of the writer. - T.: Science, 1973.-116 p.
5. Togaev O. The hero is a social phenomenon: Literary and critical articles. - Tashkent: Literature and art, 1985. - 190 p.
6. Kholmirzaev Sh. Kholmirzayev Sh. Make a Bridge: Novel. - Tashkent: Literature and Art, 1984.-384 p.
7. Sharafutdinov O. Loyalty to the truth.- Tashkent: Literature and art, 1988.- P. 315.
8. Hamidova M.O. Shukur Kholmirzaev's ability to create the character of a national hero // Berlin SCIENCE, RESEARCH, DEVELOPMENT# 25.- 30.01.2020-31.01.2020.- B.209-214.
9. Hamidova M. The artistic and stylistic uniqueness of Shukur Kholmirzaev's stories // Bulletin of Namangan State University, 2021.- No. 4.- B.331.